

APPLICATION OF ATOMISTIC ELEMENT ANALYSIS IN NANO-SIMULATIONS

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SUMMARY: An atomistic finite element approach has recently been developed for nano-simulation. Two types of elements were established: chemical bond and van der Waals bond. The stiffness matrixes of these elements were formulated based upon relations between bond deformations and restoration forces or moments. Once element stiffness matrixes are established, a procedure, similar to conventional finite element analysis, can be employed to assemble a global stiffness matrix. Boundary conditions can then be applied. Thus, stress-strain relations can be derived based upon the dimension change of the atomistic material domain in response to external load. The new approach can be employed for both static and dynamic analysis. In order to demonstrate the approach, deformations of idealized polymer fields were simulated. The stress-strain curve was derived and the progressive development of damage and failure was observed step by step. In addition, stress derived from boundary conditions was compared to atomic stress.

KEYWORDS: Atomistic FE Method, Atomic Stress, Nano-Simulation.

INTRODUCTION

With the increased attention to nanostructured materials, where inhomogeneities approach molecular dimension, methods are needed that relate atomic-level forces and displacements to macroscopic stresses, strains, and failure processes. Recently, an atomistic finite element approach [1-2] has been developed to simulate the deformation of nano-materials. There are two types of atomistic elements: chemical bond and van der Waals bond. The stiffness matrixes of these elements were formulated based upon relations between bond deformations and restoration forces or moments. Once element stiffness matrixes are established, a procedure, similar to conventional finite element analysis, can be employed to assemble a global stiffness matrix. Boundary conditions can then be applied and stress-strain relations derived.

One of the most common approaches in nano-simulation is molecular dynamics. It is based upon classical equations of motion for a system of particles, such as atoms or united atoms. Atomic positions are typically derived using an explicit procedure, called the Verlet algorithm [3], derived from the second Newtonian law:

$$\mathbf{a}_i(t) = \sum_{j \neq i} \frac{\mathbf{f}_{ij}(t)}{m_i} \quad (1)$$

$\mathbf{a}_i(t)$ is the acceleration of atom i , m_i is the mass of atom i , and \mathbf{f}_{ij} is the force on atom i due to atom j . Expressing acceleration as the second derivative of the position vector, one can derive the Verlet equation as

$$\mathbf{r}_i(t + \Delta t) = 2\mathbf{r}_i(t) - \mathbf{r}_i(t - \Delta t) + \sum_{j \neq i} \frac{\mathbf{f}_{ij}(t)}{m_i} (\Delta t)^2$$

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